

Laptop Distribution Among Engineering Graduate Students in Chhattisgarh: A Brief Perspective.

Dr. J. Durga Prasad Rao

Additional Director & HOD Computer Science,
Shri Shankaracharya Mahavidyalaya, Junwani, Bililai.

Pranjali Dewangan

Asst. Professor,
Pt. Harishankar Shukla Memorial College, Raipur.

INTRODUCTION

Engineering College reform has been a subject of ceaseless dialog since the inceptions of the Indian education system. Today's Engineering Colleges are a clear reflection of the vision of Horace Mann and his efforts to usher in the normal Engineering College era. However, the tools and resources available to today's Engineering foundations are immense and often divergent from the core educational modules of Mann's time when just written work and reading were required to be instructed (Hinsdale, 1898). The quick pace of ever-changing technology exaggerates this phenomenon. Often, the emphasis on e-learning has led educators to place very much an excessive amount of emphasis on the "e" and not upon the real learning which we are attempting to foster (Garrison, D. R. (2011). As technology is adopted, it is imperative that educators have a comprehensive knowledge of both the technology being adopted, and where it fits into the pedagogical process.

The purpose of this review was to pick up a better understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of Laptop dispersion, the people driving these decisions, and the technological qualities that have been driving the reception

process of laptop devices inside the Engineering landscape of Technical Engineering Colleges located in the Chhattisgarh state of India. The intent was to better pinpoint the gatherings and people who have been influencing educational technology leaders to receive laptop devices and to better understand the scope of influence in which each of these gatherings really holds amid the selection process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Vision of a 21st Century Educational Environment

It has been argued that for now's students to successfully develop and become tomorrow's workforce, they should be prepared to work inside an ever-changing world where the capacity to consume and process information is the key to success. Furthermore, researchers have stated that students must develop the capacity to become "expert thinkers" (Levy, F., and Murnane, R. J. (2006).) where they should demonstrate the capacity to fundamentally interpret information from multiple sources. Advocates of 21st century learning environments have proposed that students who neglect to learn these skills may end up tumbling to the base of the employment ladder, greatly constraining their career alternatives and lifetime earnings. Also, impediments upon their career alternatives will be a result of interconnectedness of our international economy that will demand that tomorrow's workforce possess the skills and competencies necessary to collaborate with coworkers connecting disciplines and geographic areas. Educational scholars have maintained that this will require students to have a deep understanding of their content areas, a commitment to interpersonal relationships, and the dedication necessary to tie the two together in a meaningful, productive manner (ERA, C. L. M. I. A, 2013).

Mobile Learning

Mobile learning, or M-Learning, is a term that has been coined to describe a derivation of E-Learning that is facilitated using a mobile device. Thusly, mobile learning has been defined as the transfer of information, knowledge, content and skills using mobile devices that replace other types

of print and digital media to facilitate the learning process. Mobile devices regularly have included, yet were not limited to, personal information aides, Laptop computers (Apple iPad, Google Android devices and Windows 8) and cellular phones, all running an extent of operating systems.

Early Technologies Leveraged for Mobile Learning

Since the presentation of the personal information partner (PDA), many ground breaking educators have dreamed of universal access to affordable electronic instructional devices. Chief among the devices that offered a glimpse into the next decade of development was the Apple Newton Messagepad 2100 first introduced in 1993 and discontinued four years later (Pace, S. (2008)). This device offered the promise of inkwell technology that converted a user's penmanship into a method of text info. Unfortunately, the technology was very early in the design stage and rarely functioned as intended. However, the model of handheld mobile computing devices that easily provided for human computer interaction was a powerful concept for some educators. Taking after the Newton, different incarnations emerged, each having unique features and differing ranges of success. Examples of such include the Palm Pilot and the Compaq iPad, which offered an early version of the Windows Mobile operating system. As these devices continued to develop and evolve, features, for example, device to computer synchronization, infrared information exchange, Wi-Fi information transfer, and cellular connectivity were added to augment the devices features.

Teacher Acceptance and Other Barriers

Teacher acceptance of new technologies has verifiably hinged upon a number of factors. A considerable lot of these factors have been observed to be characteristic for the technology itself and others have stemmed from the vantage purpose of the user themselves. To begin to explore this relationship, researchers often lead what are termed ease of use studies upon a given technology. In describing ease of use in devices, for example, Laptops, there are a number of

standardized methods in which to gage such convenience. While such studies are commonplace inside the technology business arena to help refine and enhance items for the marketplace, the use of such frameworks is relatively rare inside ENGINEERING educational environments.

METHODOLOGY

Null Hypotheses Listing

H01 There is no significant difference between the attributes being cited as perceived pressure sources regarding purchase of Laptop technologies.

H02 There is no significant difference between the attributes being cited as perceived pressure sources regarding purchase of Laptop technologies when compared to corporation enrollment size.

H03 There is no significant difference between the attributes listed as educational reasons being cited as benefits of Laptop technologies.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Null Hypotheses One (H01) was formulated as takes after: There is no significant difference between the attributes being cited as perceived pressure sources regarding the purchase of Laptop technologies. Because three items tested achieved measurable significance, the research data supported the rejection of H01.

The data received in response to question 3 (Social/Political Influences) was then examined based upon four groupings comprising of Engineering Colleges reporting less than 1,500 students (very little companies), 1,500 to 2,999 students (little partnerships), 3,000 to 5,999 students (medium organizations) and, in conclusion, an aggregate student enrollment of 6,000 and over (large enterprises). As indicated in Table 4.1, the ANOVA and Scheffe' post hoc tests revealed that there were measurably significant differences between gatherings in questions 3.7 and 3.10 when contrasting responses utilizing enterprise size as an independent variable.

Table 4.1

Scheffé post hoc criterion for significance
based upon college size

To what degree do you agree with the following statements:			95% Confidence Interval			
			Mean		Lower Upper	
			Difference	SE	Bound	Bound
I have received pressure from Higher Education members to implement laptop devices	Very Small	Small	-0.89	0.32	-1.80	.03
		Medium	-0.36	0.37	-1.41	.69
		Large	0.46	0.38	-.60	1.53
I perceived pressure from my superintend est to implement laptop devices	Small	Very Small	0.89	0.32	-.03	1.80
		Medium	0.53	0.39	-.58	1.63
		Large	1.35*	0.40	.23	2.47
I perceived pressure from my superintend est to implement laptop devices	Medium	Very Small	0.36	0.37	-.69	1.41
		Small	-0.53	0.39	-1.63	.58
		Large	0.82	0.43	-.41	2.06
I perceived pressure from my superintend est to implement laptop devices	Large	Very Small	-0.46	0.38	-1.53	.60
		Small	-1.35*	0.40	-2.47	-.23
		Medium	-0.82	0.43	-2.06	.41
I perceived pressure from my superintend est to implement laptop devices	Very Small	Small	-1.03*	0.34	-2.00	-.05
		Medium	0.21	0.39	-.90	1.32
		Large	0.46	0.40	-.67	1.59
I perceived pressure from my superintend est to implement laptop devices	Small	Very Small	1.03*	0.34	.05	2.00
		Medium	1.24*	0.42	.06	2.41
		Large	1.49*	0.42	.30	2.68
I perceived pressure from my superintend est to implement laptop devices	Medium	Very Small	-0.21	0.39	-1.32	.90
		Small	-1.24*	0.42	-2.41	-.06
		Large	0.46	0.40	-.67	1.59

* p<0.05

Null Hypotheses Two (H02) was formulated as takes after: There is no significant difference between the attributes being cited as perceived pressure sources regarding purchase of Laptop technologies when compared to partnership enrollment size. Because three of the items tested achieved measurable significance, the research data supported the rejection of H02.

Table 4.2

Results of all responses to question 4 perceived educational benefits influencing laptop purchases displaying statistical significance

To what degree do you agree with the following statement:	N	M	SE M	SD	Sk	SE	r
Laptop technologies improve classroom instruction	138	4.17	.09	1.00	-.43	.21	-2.09
Laptop technologies increase the differentiation of instruction	138	4.50	.10	1.12	-.64	.21	-3.10
Implementing laptop technologies lowers printing costs	138	4.07	.11	1.30	-.46	.21	-2.25
Implementing laptop technologies improves teacher-student communication	138	4.17	.10	1.16	-.42	.21	-2.02

contd..

Implementing laptop technologies improves student collaboration	138	4.45	.10	1.17	-.80	.21	-3.89
Implementing laptop technologies increases student involvement in classroom activities	138	4.50	.09	1.10	-.80	.21	-3.86
Implementing laptop technologies lowers district expenditures on technology	138	2.51	.12	1.36	.86	.21	4.18
Laptop technologies receive positive public responses	138	4.14	.09	1.00	-.87	.21	-4.23
Laptop technologies are essential to the adoption of digital textbooks	138	3.96	.12	1.40	-.42	.21	-2.04
Laptop technologies increase student learning outside of school hours	138	4.05	.10	1.17	-.62	.21	-3.02
Laptop technologies are still limited to student tasks regarding the viewing of media and basic research (examples: watching videos, web browsing)	138	4.73	.10	1.12	-1.33	.21	-6.45

Null Hypotheses Three (H03) was formulated as takes after: There is no significant difference between the attributes listed as educational reasons being cited as the benefits of Laptop technologies. Because nine of the items tested achieved measurable significance, the research data supported the rejection of H03.

Processing ANOVA tests on the results did not return any items of measurable significance. All things considered, the Scheffe' post hoc tests were unnecessary as there was no factual significances found between the four gatherings.

CONCLUSIONS, DISCUSSION, AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Review of Hypothesis Testing

When testing the invalid hypotheses against enterprise size four examined groupings were utilized comprising of Engineering Colleges reporting 1,500 or fewer students (very little companies), 1,500 to 2,999 students (little organizations), 3,000 to 5,999 students (medium partnerships) and, finally, an aggregate student enrollment of 6,000 and over (large organizations). H01. There is no significant difference between the attributes being cited as perceived pressure sources regarding purchase of Laptop technologies.

Given that each of these items was positively skewed, while taking into account the

rejection of the invalid hypothesis, the results indicated that these were not factors influencing the purchase of Laptop technologies. In that capacity, the research supported the rejection of H01.

H02. There is no significant difference between the attributes being cited as perceived pressure sources regarding purchase of Laptop technologies when compared to corporation enrollment size. Here the differences of the means all indicated that technology leaders in little locale reported perceiving higher levels of pressure from their superintendents to implement Laptop technologies. In that capacity, the research supported the rejection of H02.

H03. There is no significant difference between the attributes listed as educational reasons being cited as benefits of Laptop technologies

Numerous responses to this battery of questions achieved measurable significance. Among the ten items perceived to be benefits were:

- Improvement to classroom guideline
 - Increase in differentiation of guideline
 - Lowers printing costs
 - Improvement of teacher-student correspondence
 - Enhanced student cooperation
 - Better student classroom involvement
 - Positive Technical response to the technologies
 - Essential to the selection of digital textbooks
 - Enhancement of student learning outside of Engineering College hours
 - Devices are well suited to consume media
- In that capacity, the research supported the rejection of H03.

RECOMMENDATIONS

One item that was observed to be lost from this study was that the survey neglected to inquire whether participants were self-motivated to recommend the purchase of Laptop technologies. This is an undeniable piece of information that is absent from this study which would help give better knowledge into the social/political factors. It may be discovered that if educational technology leaders were all by themselves the sources of

social/political pressures, then they may not report other types of external pressures as they would observe such factors to be congruent with their own particular beliefs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study is part of UGC Sponsored project entitled "Analyzing the Advantages and Disadvantages of Laptop Distribution among Engineering Graduate Students: With Special Reference to Chhattisgarh State." The first author is thankful to UGC committee for sponsoring the project, Principal for assistance in doing project, Members for supporting in completion of the project.

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